

The Future of Nation – States in Africa Beyond the 21st Century: Federalism or Secession?

Author Details:

Thomas Otieno Juma-(PhD Political Science – Kisii University); Lecturer, Political Science – Moi University.

Abstract:

This paper underscores that nation – states are very important fabrics of polity given that their existence and form determine and shape them for sovereign endowments and ultimately international politics. The future of nation – states hinges on their historical formation and progressive efforts put in nurturing their being. In asking what makes states exist or disappear and whether nation – states exist in Africa becomes a good starting point in building a thought into this thesis. In addition to this, the author would want to find projections of future existence of nation – states in Africa 21st Century and secondly, carrying out a politico – surgical analysis of African states and nation – state formations after independence. With this limited yet wide in scope summaries are made. The study finds this subject appealing because the concept nation – state seems to portend a gap in knowledge as currently used. This makes their existence is an issue for political scientists and other disciplines and more so in the African parlance. This will open a prism through which therefore the future of nation – states in Africa can be viewed now whether in stable units or through likely disintegrations of federalism or secession in the 21st century. The research will employ a qualitative inquiry on the basis of written material available and relevant to the thought which shall then be reviewed in context, form, and content to arrive at conclusions

Key Words: Nations, Nation – states, Self – determination, Secession, Ethnicity, Nationalism, Federalism, Kenya, Africa

Background

The application of the words nation, nation – states, countries, and republics have been used quiet often to almost mean the same thing. For legalities both at local politics and in international politics their uses have meanings to the practice of politics. It is also important at the very onset to point that these entities have always existed or disappeared. Whereas nations exist whether spoken (has to do with arrangements that don't meet the threshold but coexist harmoniously or otherwise) or in reality, republics (existence where supreme power is held by the people and their elected representatives, and case two where an elected or nominated leader – a president is in charge) do exist. Republics can also mean groups that possess certain equality between its members within a prescribed boundary. Whichever system they take, they are countries whose 'FORMS' will dictate their harmony or disharmony, a product of many factors. The question of existence of nation – states in Africa is what many scholars are in contention with.

As the world or rather the global system of states age in the 21st century do the challenges of the present require old conceptions in understanding and for explanations. The concept nation – state is a 17th century phenomenon that arose in Europe to define and shape international system. Prior to that there were marked build – ups of nationalism towards being distinct and to self preserve, necessitating collisions and conflicts for survival. The concept of nation – state then becomes more clearer with the dawn of 18th century to describe modernity. I want to state categorically in this paper that whereas the 17th Century was the Western Europe era as to nation – states, the Eastern Europe attained this status in the 20th Century (early 1990s) with the fall of communism. It is however, likely that the 21st Century will be Africa's moment for nation – states due to the renaissance of nationalism against the Berlin and independent outfits. In addition to this fact, the big countries in Africa might just need to be cut to sizeable portions of land to make it easy for leaders to manage them effectively as some European states are but within the nation – state context to create homogeneity towards development.

Wimmer and Feinstein (2010), the French and American revolutions of the late-eighteenth century gave birth to the ideal of the modern nation-state—an independent state with a written constitution, ruled in the name of a nation of equal citizens. During those days, all other states were still governed on the basis of other principles of legitimacy. In dynastic states, a prince was entitled to assume the mantle of power upon the death of his father (as in the multiethnic Habsburg and Ethiopian empires); in theocracies, religious leaders guided their flocks in worldly matters as well (e.g., in Tibet and Montenegro); Ottoman and Spanish elites spread the true faith across the globe, British governors brought progress to “backward” peoples in far-away places, and, during the twentieth century, the party cadres of the Soviet Union advanced a revolutionary, transnational project in the name of the world’s working classes. Kings, theocrats, and imperial elites attempted to extend their states’ boundaries irrespective of the ethnic backgrounds of those who came under their rule. Compare that situation to the world today: empires have dissolved, theocracies have been dethroned, and only a handful of countries, mostly in the Middle East, are still governed as absolutist monarchies comparable to prerevolutionary France, where the king ruled in the name of God and represented the House of Bourbon, not the French nation.

The principles of the above assertions for modern nation - states are embedded on entities which espouse equality of citizens and constitutions which give legitimacy. The dilution of the notion nation – states did not take long for the seemingly emerging empires which in the bid to perpetuate the new concept became concerned with spheres of influence without respecting the Euro-model. On the overall, nation – states would exist if the political entity of a state is conjoined to the cultural entity of a nation. According to Anthony Smith, one of the most influential scholars of nation-states and nationalism, argued that a state is a nation-state only if and when a single ethnic and cultural population inhabits the boundaries of a state, and the boundaries of that state are coextensive with the boundaries of that ethnic and cultural population. This is a very narrow definition that presumes the existence of the “one nation, one state” model. Consequently, less than 10% of states in the world meet its criteria. Despite this fact, many stable states are near nation – states in the sense that there a major dominant nation. Most commonly, the idea of a nation-state was and is associated with the rise of the modern system of states, often called the “Westphalian system” in reference to the Treaty of Westphalia (1648). Nation-states typically have a more centralized and uniform public administration than their imperial predecessors because they are smaller and less diverse (www.nation-states-and-sovereignty)

The central question in understanding nationalism (Smith, 1994) is the role of the past in the creation of the present. This has brought sharp divisions between theorists of nationalism. Nationalists, perennialists, modernists and post-modernists have presented us with very different interpretations of that role. The manner in which they have viewed the place of ethnic history has largely determined their understanding of nations and nationalism today. For nationalists, the role of the past is clear and unproblematic. The nation was always there, indeed it is part of the natural order, even when it was submerged in the hearts of its members. The task of the nationalist is simply to remind his or her compatriots of their glorious past, so that they can recreate and relive those glories. Perennialists, think the nation is immemorial. National forms may change and particular nations may dissolve, but the identity of a nation is unchanging. Modernist, on the other hand view the past as largely irrelevant. The nation is a modern phenomenon, the product of nationalist ideologies, which themselves are the expression of modern, industrial society. The nationalist is free to use ethnic heritages, but nation-building can proceed without the aid of an ethnic past. To the post-modernist, the past is more problematic hence nations are modern and the product of modern cultural conditions, the present creates the past in its own image. They think of imagined political community.

Very importantly again to consider is Fichte (1806), the first, original, and truly natural boundaries of states are beyond doubt their internal boundaries. Those who speak the same language are joined to each other by a multitude of invisible bonds by nature herself, long before any human art begins; they understand each other and have the power of continuing to make themselves understood more and more clearly; they belong together and are by nature one and an inseparable whole. Such a whole, if it wishes to absorb and mingle with itself any

other people of different descent and language, cannot do so without itself becoming confused, in the beginning at any rate, and violently disturbing the even progress of its culture.

Statement of the Problem

The study seeks to move in a constructivist trajectory that without a clear understanding of the concept nation or nation – state, there can be none. Constructivism must be founded on knowledge basis consistent with available empiricism. With this eminent gap among historians, sociologists, and political scientists; sometimes the word has been distanced from what it is and often colloquial statements as “ethnicity is bad”, forgetting ethnicity has to do with nations take academic regime. Though understood in some dimensions, the statement refers to unwanted practices in a mixed – multinational environment but reference of states/ countries to mean nations perse without politico – surgical analysis distorts the concept of constructivism. The study introspects the subject because the concept nation – state seems to be inappropriately used and therefore empirical understanding can rectify it in meaning in the African parlance and beyond. This then will open a prism through which the future of nation – states in Africa can be viewed more clearly. The study is concerned whether the future of nation – states will be stable units or likely disintegrate through federalism and secession in the 21st century as serious neo – nationalism where most nations in need of space due to regime related aspects agitate and others due to induced dysfunctions of republics think unitary states otherwise. The future of nation – states hinges on their historical formation and progressive efforts put in nurturing their being.

Study Objectives

The objectives to guide this study were;

- i. To find the general causes of existence of nation – states in Africa;
- ii. To examine the failures of the independence era (1960s) nation – state formations in Africa;
- iii. To carry out a politico – surgical analysis of African states after independence;
- iv. To establish the types of self –determination (federalism or secession) in terms of their types, theories, and conditions.

Methodology

This study employed qualitative inquiry on the basis of written material available and relevant to the thought which was then reviewed in context, form, and content in line with the conclusions.

Discourse Analysis

This section carries out an elaborate exposition of the subject matter under discussion as recorded by other scholars and the author’s views (criticisms, critique, and persuasions from the written work). This will follow the order of the study objectives highlighted above.

Projections of future existence of nation – states in Africa 21st Century;

It would be prudent to understand as an introductory conjecture to clarify some of the pertinent terminologies that will be commonly used in this discourse in a way of creating distinctions where necessary.

A state may be construed to mean, according to Dr. Paul M. Johnson; A territory built by conquest in which one culture, one set of ideals and one set of laws have been imposed by force or threat over diverse nations by a civilian and military bureaucracy. States are ephemeral and originate and disappear with the stroke of a pen (e.g.

the end of the U.S.S.R., December 25, 1991). It can however be differentiated from an independent state which on the other hand is a specialized type of political organization characterized by a full-time, specialized, professional work force of tax-collectors, soldiers, policemen, bureaucrats and the like that exercises supreme political authority over a defined territory with a permanent population, independent from any enduring external political control and possessing a local predominance of coercive power (always supplemented with moral and remunerative incentives as well) great enough to maintain general obedience to its laws or commands within its territorial borders.

The first known states were created in ancient times in Egypt, Mesopotamia, India, China, Mexico and Peru, but it is only in relatively modern times that states have almost completely displaced alternative "stateless" forms of political organization of societies all over the planet. (Roving bands of hunter-gatherers and even fairly sizable and complex tribal societies based on herding or agriculture have existed without any full-time specialized state organization, and these "stateless" forms of political organization have in fact prevailed for all of the prehistory and much of the history of the human species.) Nations and states may seem identical, but they aren't. And the distinction is more than purely academic. "States" govern a territory with boundaries. They have laws, taxes, officials, currencies, postal services, police and (usually) armies. They wage war, negotiate treaties, put people in prison and regulate life in thousands of ways. They claim "sovereignty" within their territory, a kind of exclusive jurisdiction that goes back to the rule of kings.

"Nations" by contrast are groups of people claiming common bonds like language, culture and historical identity. Benedict Anderson calls them "imagined communities." Some groups claiming to be nations have a state of their own, like the French, Dutch, Egyptians and Japanese. Others want a state but do not have one: East Timorese, Tibetans, Chechnyans and Palestinians for example. Others don't want statehood but claim and enjoy some autonomy.

The Sioux are a nation within the boundaries of the United States, the Catalan within Spain, and the Scots within Britain. Each of these nations has its own special territory, rights, laws and culture but not statehood. In East Africa some well structured known nations which have been submerged under multi-national states against their wish, Buganda continue to fight retention of old glory to no success. Some imagined nations are larger than states or cross state boundaries. The "Arab nation" embraces more than a dozen states, while the nation of the Kurds takes in large chunks of four states. There can be sharp differences about the legitimacy of states and nations, both within and outside of their territory.

Most people assume that nation-states are fixed and permanently-established across most of the globe. But actually states are in constant flux. State boundaries are arbitrary and often changed -- by war, negotiation, arbitration and even by sale of territory for money (Russia sold Alaska to the United States, for example). Mapmakers get headaches (and extra sales) from the constant changes. Peru and Ecuador had a brief war in 1995 over their jungle border. Argentina and Chile disagree on control of icy and uninhabited lands in the far south. Japan pressures Russia over control of the Kuriles to its north. Former Yugoslavia collapsed into a welter of competing claims to sovereignty, a mess of unsettled borders and bloody battles to prove who ruled over what.

A nation-state is a state, or country, that has defined borders and territory. It is additionally a country in which a nation of principally the same type of people exists, organized by either race or cultural background. In the nation-state, generally, everyone would speak the same language, probably practice the same or similar types of religion, and share a set of cultural, "national," values. In fact, most countries do not completely fall within the definition of the nation-state, since most countries have immigrants. Once immigrants come to a country, especially in large numbers, the nation-state can no longer exist. Countries with only a small number of immigrants may still be seen as containing predominantly the same ethnicity and shared culture and may thus be considered as approaching the theoretical nation-state.

Iceland is considered almost an ideal nation – state since immigration to Iceland is quite low. Japan also comes close to being a nation-state because the sense of national identity and shared language is very strong. It is not coincidental that both of these countries are islands and thus less “crossing of the border” can exist.

History has it that the desire to establish a nation-state if not conventionally undertaken can be one of the most devastating one and may result in either mass eviction of other nationalities or ethnic cleansing. Hitler attempted to establish Germany as a nation – state by first exiling Jews, and then ultimately, by killing the majority of Jewish residents in Germany, and in other countries he conquered like Poland. Attempting to enforce a nation-state where none truly exists often results in high numbers of deaths for large minority populations and a lack of humanity to the extreme. As devastating as it may be, the handling and practice of politics determine the acceleration or not of the idea. Though Hitler and others have attempted creation of clean race, it is not possible but what many scholars on nation – states agree on is that there can never be pure states of this kind except the existence of one dominant nation is what it yields to. In Portugal the Portuguese are way above 90% thus a nation – state. France on the other hand is dominant to the extent that the next bigger ‘nation’ are about 10%.

It is on the basis above that Kenya being one of the existing multi-national states has suffered and develops interest to a renaissance that will reduce if not complete the erstwhile hostilities arising from incompatibilities of societies historical in nature through cohesion. That desired co-existence cannot bear much fruit unless it is experiential. True to this, the many years of independence upto 2007 reignited the dire need of a nation- state in Kenya. Whereas to others it comes by independence, still to some cultural collisions become a path. The perceived “African States” yet multinational states, Kenya among them might soon start to experience statehood. A paradox! What we normally call the problem of tribalism is a serious clash of nations. More to it, one can term it further as unchecked and uncontrolled clash or even encouraged clash.

After the long general view of causes of nation – states from across the global divide, specificity as to existence of the same in Africa is paramount. The causes can be pointed out to include; history of nations (ethnicities or *in derogative term – ‘tribe’*) and the reign of independent regimes. To look at each briefly requires the benefit of appreciation of scholarly discourses on the same. Africa historically has been a home of great historic nations which later disintegrated due to growth and external influence and interaction. The narration about these episodes are both ancient, medieval, and contemporary. Historians can subject the gaps to further study to bring in historical details not captured by the analysis.

Andrews (2017) avers that, Histories of early African civilizations often focus solely on ancient Egypt, but the continent was home to several other powerful empires (call them nations) that controlled trade routes, built sprawling cities and crafted architectural monuments that still stand today. From ancient Sudan to medieval Zimbabwe. He periodizes nations to early empires as follows;

1. The Kingdom of Kush stood as a regional power in Africa for over a thousand years. This ancient Nubian empire reached its peak in the second millennium B.C., when it ruled over a vast swath of territory along the Nile River in what is now Sudan. The kingdom was both a trading partner and a military rival of Egypt—it even ruled Egypt as the 25th Dynasty—and it adopted many of its neighbor’s customs.
2. Mysterious Punt kingdom historically dates to around 2500 B.C., when it appears in Egyptian records as a “Land of the Gods” rich in ebony, gold, myrrh and exotic animals such as apes and leopards. The Egyptians are known to have sent huge caravans and flotillas on trade missions to Punt—most notably during the 15th century B.C. The site of the fabled kingdom is believed to have existed somewhere on the Red Sea coast of East Africa.

3. Rome's rival in the Punic Wars, Carthage was a North African commercial hub that flourished for over 500 years. The city-state began its life in the 8th or 9th century B.C. as a Phoenician settlement in what is now Tunisia, but it later grew into a sprawling seafaring empire that dominated trade in textiles, gold, silver and copper. At its peak, nearly half a million inhabitants and 220 ships were protected in harbors on its bays. Its influence extended to Spain and parts of the Mediterranean, but its thirst for expansion led to increased friction with the burgeoning Roman Republic.
4. At the time Roman Empire rose and fell, influential Kingdom of Aksum held sway over parts of what are now Eritrea and northern Ethiopia. By the 2nd and 3rd centuries A.D. it was a trading juggernaut whose gold and ivory made it a vital link between ancient Europe and the Far East. In the 4th century, Aksum became one of the first empires in the world to adopt Christianity, which led to a political and military alliance with the Byzantines.
5. The founding of the Mali Empire dates to the 1200s, when a ruler named Sundiata Keita—sometimes called the “Lion King”—led a revolt against a Sosso king and united his subjects into a new state. Under Keita and his successors, the empire tightened its grip over a large portion of West Africa, it had institutions such as Timbuktu's Sankore University with a library with an estimated 700,000 manuscripts. The Mali Empire eventually disintegrated in the 16th century.
6. Few states in African history can compare to the Songhai Empire. Formed in the 15th century from some of the former regions of the Mali Empire, this West African kingdom was larger than Western Europe and comprised parts of a dozen modern day nations. The empire enjoyed a period of prosperity thanks to vigorous trade policies and a sophisticated bureaucratic system that separated its vast holdings into different provinces, each ruled by its own governor. It reached its zenith in the early 16th century under King Muhammad I Askia. While the Songhai Empire was once among the most powerful states in the world, it later crumbled in the late 1500s after a period of civil war and internal strife
7. One of the most impressive monuments in sub-Saharan Africa is the Great Zimbabwe. As an indigenous empire it thrived in the region between the 13th and 15th centuries. This kingdom ruled over a large chunk of modern day Botswana, Zimbabwe and Mozambique. It was mysteriously abandoned sometime in the 15th century after the kingdom went into decline, but in its heyday it was home to an estimated 20,000 people.

In later years, Falola and Fleming (2017) points that African civilizations underwent many changes since the continent's first set of people began the process of state formation. An analysis of civilization throughout the African continent stresses the resiliency and ability of the African peoples to adapt from early state formation to the present day. Though Westerners often tend to view it as one “country” and lump its peoples together as Africans, Africa is a huge continent (second only to Asia). These generalizations oversimplify African civilizations and the continent's diversity. African environments comprise incredibly diverse people speaking more than 800 languages which are rather difficult to address as a cohesive African civilization. In line with the thesis in this paper, the deconstruction must begin from where Africa in its form stopped which Falola and Fleming confirms; adaptation ability is superb yet the lumping of Africa's civilization affects and oversimplifies her later state formations neglecting the form – state.

A politico – surgical analysis of African states and nation – state formations after independence;

The failures of independent era into the notion, nation – state is a failure of joint and various if am to borrow that terminology. Skalník (2002), reasons his confusions in regard to the use of kingdoms and monarchies and concludes they were just states, which carried various epithets such as primitive, archaic, traditional, tribal or early to distinguish them from the modern state. Let us attempt a deconstruction of the concepts kingdom and

chiefdom in Africa. The main thrust of theory appeared in the 1960s. Without giving much reason why they used ‘kingdoms’ and ‘kings’ in their comparative surveys and collections instead of chiefdoms or states, the anthropologists Richards (1961), Forde and Kaberry (1967), Mair (1977) as well as the historian Vansina (1962) in Skalnik, must have been aware that their conceptual framework of kingdom was hardly innovative. The researcher therefore concludes on this terminology from early literature that the reconstruction into the concept which is a deconstruction of the earlier implied use (kingdoms/ monarchies/ chiefdoms) meant states under one nation (nation – states).

From much silent scholarly work, I can say that the problem of African countries of nations in need of space lies in our ignorance as elites to thinking of state reconstruction after the colonialists finished their agenda with what they called states – the existing countries. I consider my continent Africa as “*a continent stuck in the colonial industrialization and developmental history*”. This tie with what Green (2010) suggests; while recent historical scholarship has attempted to read back the existence of nations into medieval Europe, a similar revisionism has yet to take place amongst scholars of Africa. Here I take up the case of Buganda, a pre-colonial kingdom on the northern edge of Lake Victoria in what is now central Uganda. I show that Buganda in the mid-19th century fits various definitions of both ethnic groups and nations, while its neighbors largely do not. Thus the Bugandan case both demonstrates further evidence for the existence of pre-modern nations.

From being seen a generation or two ago as a continent full of “tribes,” Africa has more recently been re-examined in light of Western theories of ethnicity and nationhood. Since the late 1960s and early 1970s “tribes” have been replaced by “ethnic groups” in the literature, while at the same time a burgeoning literature on ethnicity and nationalism in Africa has emerged (Berman, Eyoh, and Kymlicka, 2004). These new discoveries have made African ethnic groups (nations) more closer and even much more when faced with political challenges within the countries where they have found themselves.

Outstandingly, yet within this increasingly large body of scholarship (Gillingham, 1999) there has sadly been little attempt to understand the concept of nationhood as applied to pre-colonial Africa. This is surprising in light of recent work which has argued for the existence of a select number of nations in medieval Europe, whose state formations have long been considered at least somewhat comparable to those in pre-colonial Africa (Beattie, 1964). The one exception to this lacuna is Adrian Hastings’s (1997), ‘The Construction of Nationhood’, whose analysis of medieval England (on which he spends two chapters) or Europe more generally (four chapters) is considerably more detailed than his discussion of pre-colonial Africa (one chapter). Attempts in the post-colonial period at fashioning supra-ethnic national identities, however, have largely failed, with many African states caught up in ethnic violence and conflict at various points in time.

A common question that some people have asked due to misinformation or lack of information and which the political class in developing countries majorly in Africa perpetuate is whether ethnicity is bad or not. The answer to this critical and foundational question is NO. Ethnicity defines the place of a single human being in existence hence it cannot be bad in anyway. I would rather explicitly suggest and affirm that it is people themselves who are bad. If ethnicity is you in corporate sense in terms of your culture, language, and history; how can it be bad? If again what you call ethnicity pertaining to another person you may share with space and geographical location is not given by man, then how can it be bad. In fact my friends in the political science know of one theory of origin of states – the divine origin. This is the far that ethnicity emanates. It is a given just as life. Your ethnicity is good and mine too.

Backward countries have always remained in the deconstructed forms of ethnicity to regard them as bad, but the few elite groups knowing the merits of self preservation have tended to preserve their groups because of the

eternal reality that they are not ephemeral as states. *This is not to say pure forms exist of ethnicity but rather the dominant forms throughout history are what we call ethnicity.* To emphasize again, may I say that the purpose of this elaborate statement is to make many of us appreciate that ethnicity is just but a description a NATION. Many writings exist and the usages of '*ethno – nationalism*' exist. Depending on their context, the hyphenation makes the two different and the first one a noun in this case is acted by the second one. Nationalism cannot be an action of ethnicity, implying it cannot be an action of itself. This long standing reasoning (ethno – nationalism) is somehow misleading. In the sense of the meaning we are repeating the same word thinking we make sense but which sense. Empirical, yes! Historical, yes! But factual, No! The interaction of new exposition and analysis as in this paper and others inform us that the two are one and the same and nationalism cannot be wished away. It is the form that must define our many failing conglomerate states in developing countries. The is of being pure as this paper has explained is neither here nor there since many times it is a justification thought after a conscious concretized group outcome in conformity to their identity.

May be the best way to begin the argument for politico – surgical analysis is to invoke Wimmer and Feinstein (2010) when they ask and comment thus; Why did the nation-state proliferate across the world over the past 200 years, replacing empires, kingdoms, city-states, and the like? Using a new dataset with information on 145 of today's states from 1816 to the year they achieved nation-statehood, we test key aspects of modernization, world polity, and historical institutionalist theories. Event history analysis shows that a nation-state is more likely to emerge when a power shift allows nationalists to overthrow or absorb the established regime. They close by affirming the ephemeral nature of states in the affirmative (the likelihood of states emerging with time). It is interesting as they further affirm that the global rise of the nation-state is driven by proximate and contextual political factors situated at the local and regional levels, in line with historical institutionalist arguments. This statement is a referee's danger card in a game of politics for the African political players to look back into history and carefully mirror their countries.

The French and American revolutions of the late-eighteenth century gave birth to the ideal of the modern nation-state—an independent state with a written constitution, ruled in the name of a nation of equal citizens. Understanding the global rise of the nation-state is one of the most formidable tasks of comparative historical sociology—on par with the analysis of the emergence of sovereign, territorial states in early modern Europe (see Tilly's [1975] pioneering work). Why did modern states—once they emerged out of the dynamics of *war-making, bureaucratic centralization, and increasing taxation*—become nation-states? This is a fundamental question that bogs many in the statescraft indeed. The three reasons that disturb the status – quo and conservatives embroiled in management of modern states. As an entity of modern politics war – what you would call conflicts of different kinds internally play a great threat to survival of these realist structures. Moreover, I can still add that how the polity handles their bureaucratic centralization to most African countries, a recipe of need for nation – states arise. The last bit of high taxation in African context can be replaced by corruption, we are yet to see such arising from this in Africa.

From the wider scholarship, to answer this question by Tilly above, this research displays two main weaknesses. First, many general theoretical statements are meant to explore universal processes that could account for the rise of the nation-state in the modern world as a whole or on examples picked selectively (Breuilly, 2005; Wimmer 2008). Second, more empirical research on particular trajectories of nation-state creation tends to the political science literature on decolonization (Spruyt 2005; Strang 1990) and nation-building (Bendix 1964) Yet another strand of scholarship investigates the historical developments that led to the collapse of the land-based Ottoman, Habsburg, or Soviet empires and subsequent waves of nation-state creation (e.g., Barkey and von Hagen 1997). These scholars suggest that looking case by case process reveals the emergence while at the same time decolonization features in much writing, for Africa in the 1960s to 1980s.

With this background, I can now project a discourse into the African states after independence. How have these states been framed, run, internal and external dynamics in relation to the populace. This marks the extent of this analysis, and a few examples will be used as case studies to enrich the discussion.

More into the wider reality vis a vis unrealities in secession talks is whether non – recognition which follow state existence can abate secession. Most general agreement is that non – recognition has never obstructed the urge to and secession itself. If anything just like multi-party politics it makes it more popular since it makes the interested quarters to experience more of the fertile nutrients for its growth and development. With many examples already witnessed in the continent;

- i. Katanga, Biafra, and Ogaden
- ii. Eritrea and South Sudan
- iii. Western Sahara

There is an exposition of by the first group of states showing the method used – war resulted to failure and this gives conservative statist reason for rejecting the idea for the bigness of the size of a country even if major parts are rendered dysfunctional due to lack of egalitarianism principles. The second group of Eritrea and South Sudan is an example of attainment of secession though again the lack of stability quickly gives skeptics justification to condemn secession without accrediting the success. In imagining their stability, a question to ask is how long did it take countries like Uganda to relatively stable state, countries like Kenya to experience what they may lose if secession takes place, etc? A few years into independence knowing the path they followed and oppression they went through (South Sudan) cannot be a justification of a failed secession but a success. Why a success? They attained self determination. What follows is the question of statescraft. Pessimistically though I may raise my informed understanding that their secession did not consider the matter of “nations” in their secession, instead they took the *model of racial and multinational secession* where the black people were seceding. This is what states planning secession should avoid. Where such is not avoided, the remedy is to form pure – federal republics that cater for these mixed nationalities in one. Their assumption was that the black people were highly oppressed hence they were one nation.

The secessions which are marred with international interest as opposed to being a people’s expression of their fundamental right have more likelihood of failure. The secession of Katanga was instigated by Tshombe with the support of the Belgian government for example was to secure control of the Congo’s mining resources for Belgian mining companies and to undermine the government of Patrice Lumumba and replace it with a pro-Belgian government in the Congo. When Lumumba was removed from power and murdered Tshombe continued to push for independence for Katanga though it ended through the intervention of the United Nations and the USA. The government of the Congo opposed the secession of Katanga. Without Katanga the Congo would lose territory with over 60% of its natural resources. Lumumba’s opposition was not strong enough on its own to stop Katanga’s secession bid as Tshombe’s regime was supported by Belgium. In a bid to get the United Nations to end the secession militarily, UN refusal forced Lumumba to seek the USSR for support. This instead embroiled the Congo in the cold war battles between the USA and the USSR. Lumumba’s leaning to the USSR made him not trusted by the USA and Western Europe being considered a communist. As long as Lumumba’s government remained in power, Tshombe’s regime in Katanga ensured a pro-Western regime in the country but with Patrice out of the picture, the USA could now apply pressure on Tshombe to end the secession of Katanga.

A number of hitherto likely successful secessions in 21st century will crumble the moment certain fundamental human rights especially to life and property are not observed. This is evidenced from the Biafran experience. In my view, Southeast leaders declared independence from Nigeria in May 1967 to form the Republic of Biafra, claiming the national government had failed to protect Igbos was not a problem itself because it was an exercise

of self - determination. Even though, the attempted secession resulted in a three-year long brutal civil war that claimed the lives of over a million people. The ultimatum of 1966 when Igbo people were forced to flee from northern Nigeria following continued massacres was the undoing. Ethiopian Ogaden's failure to secede is likened to the Dafur region in Sudan (Khartoum). The similarity is backed by states not willing to allow more secession after they have given in to one especially once they crystallize into authoritarianism. It is an ego preservation to denote survival. And in developing continent, any groups desiring secession can only benefit from an allowable window or else years might pass before actualizing this right.

Contrasting the Katanga-Biafra-Ogaden to Eritrea-South Sudan, the West Sahara is a mixture of success. It lies between recognition and non-recognition. As mentioned earlier, the later does not deter nor obstruct ensuing state from operations as an international outfit. The international system is full of contests among its players that are sorted often by making unprecedented decisions.

Ultimately, the position and belief of the OAU has never transitioned in its change of name from OAU to AU. The major objective and long standing one of OAU was Pan-Africanism. A very good philosophy towards its freedom. Scholars wonder whether it emerged to de – nationalize (ethnicize) the new states while unifying countries. Why? Because, in its new formation as AU, it recognized some deep '*African Peoples*' problems and charted a way to their solution through the ACHPR (1981 adopted in Nairobi and 1986 came to force in Banjul) yet as it states, the States Parties to assist groups self – determining, it has been a strangulating body thus contradicting its elaborate instrument which is very progressive in definition of African peoples "corporately and in isolation". To this, then, Pan – Africanism has succeeded in thwarting nationalism and by this, there is nothing to unite.

Political confusion reigns even beyond the African domain too, instead of cost analysis on conflict/ violence by Africa's development partners in thwarting self – determination, it might probably be a good strategy to yield to the aspirations and spend heavily in nation building thereafter.

Englebert (2005), a professor of African politics at Claremont College, has called "Africa's secessionist deficit." And the deficit in question refers to living standards and development generally. Englebert found, in one of the most exciting recent academic projects in academic African studies, that the unwillingness to cut African nations down in size (in other words, to let new nations form) has "contributed to its underdevelopment." This is especially true for the U.S. and Europe, which spend billions on reconstructing failed states such as the Congo. But letting these countries reform into smaller nations might actually reduce conflict, increase economic growth, and cost less in foreign aid. That, by the way, is Englebert's argument in a nutshell in his paper, "Let's Stick Together: Understanding Africa's Secessionist Deficit," published in African Affairs in July 2005.

Many observers, such as Jeffrey Herbst, author of the classic 2000 study, "States and Power in Africa," have argued that African nations are too large and would benefit, in some strategic cases, from break-up. The logic of division (Zachary, 2011) has worked in Europe. Who really considers Belgium for example, to be too small? (If anything, that country's political problems come from being too big, and it is many ways already divided in two.) Or Finland, which is home to far fewer Finnish speakers than there are Igbo speakers living in an area of Nigeria my wife sometimes calls "Igboland." And, besides, why should size be any objection in a world that cheered the birth of Slovenia and Slovakia? Did not the independence of tiny Kosovo receive the full measure of support from the very Western nations who worry that Africa might someday fracture into a hundred nations or more? A very truistic statement indeed. The remedy to Post-independent Africa might well lie in emerging small nation – states.

In as much as secession talks are not ending sooner in Africa but becoming bolder, pessimism will fasten secessions as opposed to quieting agitations. This trend by African leaders and beneficiaries of rogue regimes injustices will actually resist the current state formations which are in amoebic – mode, ever changing between

ethno - stability and instability. Kiley (1993) quoted African leaders saying, “A ‘yes’ vote could...stimulate ethnic secessionist movements from Cairo to Cape Town...the impact of their new status may be catastrophic elsewhere on the continent, where secessionist tendencies have hitherto been held back by the international community’s refusal to recognize new nations. “...independence will encourage secessionists in other African countries. Angola, Cameroon, Senegal and South Africa all face potential splits.” Temin (2010) sums that if these words were written today, one would assume they were about Sudan and the prospect that Southern Sudanese will vote to secede in the coming January referendum. But they were written in 1993, and the subject was the pending secession of Eritrea from Ethiopia.

Today, similar fears are heard concerning the possible division of Sudan. “What is happening in Sudan could become a contagious disease that affects the whole of Africa, (AFP, 2010)”. Libyan leader Col. Muammar Gaddafi recently warned. On another occasion, he predicted “the beginning of the crack in Africa’s map (Sudan Tribune, 2010)”. Algeria’s foreign minister added “this partitioning will have fatal repercussions on the African continent” (KNA, 2010) Chadian President Idriss Deby cautioned, “we all have a north and south. If we accept the breakup of Sudan, the domino effect will be inevitable and it would be a disaster for the continent”(Perdix, 2010). Secession movements (Temin, 2010) elsewhere in Africa exist today in Casamance (Senegal), Cabinda (Angola), Zanzibar (Tanzania), Somaliland (Somalia). Additionally to these, this paper points Kenya in the post 2017 August elections has unprecedentedly added to the desire to self –determination in Africa even as Nigeria’s new secession calls build strongly.

Moreover, it should be understood that reason for evolution of contemporary states and internationalization have a departure from the form of states. Traditionally, nation – states exist to provide basics which then after consolidation of form catapults need for international behaviour. Anarchy in states has no good for internationalization. A situation synonymous with pre-Westphalian order and the cause of Vienna 1814-15 must be solved for proper internationalization to suffice. This trajectory tends to address the narration by some globalization school of thought that gloss it to imagine it can suppress the objects and subjects of globalization (the states).

Nonetheless, as globalization bring economy among states closer so does politically new states (nation – states) emerge to make them better entities for global good. Dickens (1998), points out that as economic activities have become more globalized thus interdependence and interconnections among states improve. This is applicable to the international political system where national governments coexist with international organizations. Turay 2017 affirms that as globalization take place, there are also some examples of national rebuilding processes, such as reunification of Germany and the transformation of the former Soviet Union and some nations of tEastern Europe. In fact, the more powerfully people feel the action of globalization, the more they are inclined to get together in fiercely nationalistic groups – groups which get smaller and smaller as feelings in Northern Ireland.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Three issues surround many thinkers and especially legal scholars in developing world in the normal discourse of self –determination; exclusive rights, actual rights, and applicable rights. They may need much more intercourse in addition to the definition of African people as discussed in ACHPR in light of secession calls. Other terminologies that may require re-understanding include ethnicity in light of nationalism. While giving an opinion on the exclusive right, it may be understood to mean the right embedded on institutions and state organs that define corporate sovereignty. This informs me that corporate sovereignty may wither with time if certain factors to its well being are not nurtured. The actual right emanates from the beholders of sovereignty hence a given. It supersedes exclusive right in as far as it may fail to protect its source of exercisable power. Applicable right comprises how both people as sovereigns and the beneficiaries of exclusive rights may behave in relation to the norms that govern the rights once consolidated. The essence of this illustration attempts to illustrate that

secession is limited by existing exclusive rights yet not obstructed by the same since actual rights is derived from its base – people's rights (the primary sovereignty).

Miljenko (2007) asserts, six countries that were established as a result of secessions (Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Czech Republic, Slovakia and Slovenia) became new members of EU after successful democratisation and economic transition. There is no doubt that these countries are better off now than they were before secession. In addition, there is no significant movement in these countries that demands return to previous situation when these countries were part of multiethnic states. In other words, history shows that secession *might end with war and terrible human suffering* but also with a successful economic and political end.

According to Buchanan, secession should be allowed only as a remedy against ('remedial right to secession'); *unjust conquest, exploitation, threat of extermination and threat of cultural extinction* (Buchanan, 1991). Horowitz a radical critic of right to secession suggests it should be implemented only in the cases of decolonisation, when all the main actors agree concerning dissolution of a country, and occasionally by international action (Horowitz, 2003). Concerning the last exception, he does not explain the precondition for such an action, but claims such an does not require creation of certain rights. Nielsen claims that secession should be granted only for liberal democratic societies (Nielsen, 1998). Miljenko posits that secession is usually response to violence rather than a cause of violence and asks in rhetoric, had the Soviet Union used military in order to prevent secessions, who should have been blamed for the violence – the Soviet Union or secessionist republics?

What grounds can be recommended for secession? States under conflict or perfectly democratic states? Ostrowski also asks; should secession also be allowed from a country that is perfectly democratic, a country that accepts minority and individual rights, but in which majority of people is against secession of a part of that country? For example, in 1905, majority of people in Sweden (that was composed of that what is today Sweden and Norway) was probably against secession of Norway. Nevertheless, in Norway, 368,208 people voted for secession and only 272 people voted against secession! (Ostrowski, 1998). Raskin asks what Miljenko asked earlier; should have Sweden, in this case, sent military force in order to secure rule of majority, i.e. to prevent secession? The answer is definitely NO because, as J. Raskin has written, "*governmental legitimacy depends upon the affirmative consent of those who are governed*" (Raskin, 1993). Orentlicher from legal perspective affirms; "international law no longer abides colonization or forcible annexation. But if these forms of non-consensual rule cannot be reconciled with principles inherent in the right of self-determination, surely those same principles are challenged by a state's continued assertion of sovereignty over a defined population that has unambiguously rejected its authority (Orentlicher, 2003:26)." Authors who support secession usually argue in favour of referenda, as the best tool for expression of voters' opinion about secession. For example, Buchanan (1991) thinks three-quarter majority should be required (Buchanan, 1991). Norman in Miljenko argues in favour of majority of registered voters.

Weinstock also support supermajority without specificity of percentage (Weinstock, 2001). Only Beran (1998) does not demand any supermajority for secession. So, which majority should be required for secession – *simple majority of all voters, two-third majority of those who voted, two-third majority of all the voters, three-quarter majority of those who voted or three-fourth majority of all the voters?* The best procedure is to demand *two-third majority of all the voters*. The reason for this procedure is the following. Modern democracies demand supermajority for the change of constitution since secession of a territory changes constitutional arrangement of a country. In clarifying the above, the two third majority is not linked to the whole country comprising parts not seceding. This is explained by former Yugoslavia experiences, three republics that had two-third majority in referenda. The only exception was Montenegro, as already mentioned above, where less than fifty percent of all voters voted in favour of secession but secession still proceeded relatively smoothly. In Croatia, Slovenia and Macedonia more than two-third of citizens supported secession. In Croatia 88.2% of all the eligible voters

supported independence. The same figure was 86% in Slovenia and 74% in Macedonia (Mesic, 1994). The secession of these republics was not only legal but also legitimate. Only in Bosnia and Herzegovina support for secession was less than two-third (63%) (Woodward, 1995).

The last question that this paper thinks to address is whether a lower threshold of population of a region is a prequalification for secession. Independent statehood provides many privileges (for example, vote in the General Assembly of the UN) and duties (for example, to open embassies in other countries). Therefore, it is logical and probably the best lower limit would be 100,000 inhabitants and a higher limit would not be acceptable because many small countries function very well. For example, country with the highest GDP per capita in the world, Luxemburg, has only 450,000 inhabitants (World Bank, 2005).

In conglomerate states (multinational states) such as Kenya, national cohesion might not happen sooner. It might be a wish just like communism which cannot be attained and like the rest of Africa, hard considerations await statehood in the 21st century where federalism and secessions shall be the definitive aspects of the form – state. Where federalism shall not work, nation – states shall emerge. Upon solving the issue of stability of nation – states shall Daron Acemoglu and James A. Robinson masterpiece book - Why nations fail be very useful to my continent Africa. The ‘form’ state is a precursor to development.

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